

TABLE 1—MIXED LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF SOME HETEROCHELATES OF Zn(II) AND Cd(II) AT 30° (Ionic strength=0.2 M)

Ligand (L)	$\log K_{Zn,L}^{Zn^*}$	$\log K_{Zn,A,L}^{Zn,A}$ (1 : 1 : 1)	$\Delta \dagger$	$\log K_{Cd,L}^{Cd^*}$	$\log K_{Cd,A,L}^{Cd,A}$ (1 : 1 : 1)	$\Delta \dagger$
Glycine	5.22	4.11	1.11	4.22	3.55	0.67
α -Alanine	5.17	3.84	1.33	4.27	3.40	0.87
Leucine	4.74	3.54	1.21	3.92	3.00	0.92
Iso-Leucine	4.88	3.59	1.30	3.94	3.00	0.94
Valine	4.74	3.50	1.24	3.91	3.02	0.89
Serine	5.06	4.00	1.06	3.95	3.05	0.90
Threonine	5.16	4.08	1.08	4.02	3.25	0.77
Methionine	4.69	3.59	1.10	4.04	3.20	0.84

$$\dagger \Delta = \log K_{ML}^M - \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$$

* Values taken from literature for comparison.

$$\text{Deviation in } \log K_{MAL}^{MA} \pm 0.05$$

charge repulsion, other factors may also affect the mixed ligand formation constant.

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Aromatic and N-Substitution Reactions Involving Nickel and Copper Complexes of Schiff Base Derivatives of 2-Hydroxy Acetophenone

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BROMINATION occurs at the 5- or 3- and 5-positions of the ligand in a range of salicylaldiminato metal complexes¹⁻⁴. The electron density at 3 and 5 carbon of the benzene ring of the ligand is an

important factor in the success or failure of electrophilic or free radical substitutions. This electron density is dependent on the type of metal ion as well as the nature of other substituents present in the complex⁵.

No comprehensive investigation of the reactions involving bidentate Schiff base ligand complexes derived from 2-hydroxy-acetophenone has been reported. An attempt was, therefore, made to study the orientation effect by carrying out the bromination reactions on *bis*-(bidentate Schiff base)-complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II). N-Substitution reactions were carried out on brominated copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes by amine exchange. The structure of the resulting Schiff base complexes has been discussed and the mechanism of the bromination reaction has been suggested.

An investigation of bromination and amine exchange reactions involving the complex (I) is reported here.

Experimental

Bis[1-(2-hydroxy phenyl)ethylideneamine or its methyl derivatives]Cu(II) or Ni(II) were prepared as reported earlier⁶. *Bis*[1-(2-hydroxy phenyl)ethylideneoxime or its methyl derivatives]Cu(II) or Ni(II) were prepared by amine exchange method⁷. N-Bromo succinimide (Sisco), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (S.M.), sodium acetate (Pfizer) and bromine solution were used. Ethanol and chloroform were of analytical grade.

Synthesis of (i) bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromo phenyl)ethylideneamine]Cu(II), bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromo-*m*-tolyl)ethylideneamine]Cu(II) and bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromo-*p*-tolyl)ethylideneamine]Cu(II) (III) (X=H, 3- or 4-CH₃; R'=5-Br); and (ii) bis[1-(2-hydroxy-3,5-dibromo phenyl)ethylideneamine]Ni(II), bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromo-*m*-tolyl)ethylideneamine]Ni(II), bis[1-(2-hydroxy-3,5-dibromo-*p*-tolyl)ethylideneamine]Ni(II) and bis[1-(6-hydroxy-5-bromo-*m*-tolyl)ethylideneamine]Ni(II) (V) (X=H or 4-CH₃; R'=3- and 5-Br; X=3- or 5-CH₃; R'=5- or 3-Br):

N-Bromosuccinimide (1.9 g) in chloroform (50 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of bis[1-(2-hydroxy phenyl)ethylideneamine or its methyl derivatives]Cu(II) or Ni(II) Schiff base (1.0 g) in chloroform (50 ml) at r. t. and the mixture was stirred for 2 hr. The brownish yellow copper(II) and greenish or reddish nickel(II) solid compounds were filtered, washed with chloroform and air-dried.

The above *bis*-complexes were also prepared by direct treatment of Cu(II) or Ni(II) salt with brominated 2-hydroxy acetophenone or its methyl derivatives. The bromo derivatives of 2-hydroxy acetophenone were prepared as described in literature⁸.

N-Substituted compounds were prepared by treating III and V with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate. Hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3 g) in water (30 ml) and conc. sodium acetate solution were added to a suspension of III or V (1 g) in ethanol (30 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 1 hr with stirring. The solid obtained in each case was filtered, washed successively with water and ethanol and air-dried.

The complexes were analysed for metal, N, Br, C and H (in some cases). Molar conductance, magnetic moments, ir and electronic spectra were measured by usual techniques.

Results and Discussion

In these reactions the bromine radicals produced from the N-bromosuccinimide in presence of chloroform act as free radical and attach at 5 or 3 and 5-positions of benzene ring of I.

The hydrogen is removed from each of these intermediates and to succinimide. The dibromo chelates further react with Br[·] radical in the same manner resulting in the formation of tetrabromo compounds.

N-Bromo succinimide is known to react by a free radical mechanism in nonpolar solvents but the mechanism may be ionic in nature^{9,10} in polar solvents. When *bis*-imine Schiff base complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) are brominated in chloroform with neat bromine, the complex breaks down.

In the case of H, 3-methyl or 4-methyl substituted binary imine or oxime Cu(II) complexes, only monobromo complexes were formed. Bromination does not take place over benzene ring when the 5-position is occupied by the methyl group. This

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS, MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF BROMINATED *Bis* IMINE AND OXIME COPPER(II) AND NICKEL(II) SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Complex	Electronic spectral band λ_{max} nm	Magnetic moment μ_{eff} B.M.
1.	Bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromophenyl)ethylideneamine]Cu(II)	580	1.90
1a'	"	—	1.88
2.	Bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromo- <i>m</i> -tolyl)ethylideneamine]Cu(II)	570	1.89
3.	Bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromo- <i>p</i> -tolyl)ethylideneamine]Cu(II)	580	1.87
3b'	"	580	1.90
4.	Bis[1-(6-hydroxy- <i>m</i> -tolyl)ethylideneamine]Cu(II)	560	1.85
5.	Bis[1-(2-hydroxy-3,5-dibromo-phenyl)ethylideneamine]Ni(II)	550	Diamagnetic
6.	Bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromo- <i>m</i> -tolyl)ethylideneamine]Ni(II)	560	Diamagnetic
6a'	"	—	"
7.	Bis[1-(2-hydroxy-3,5-dibromo- <i>p</i> -tolyl)ethylideneamine]Ni(II)	550	Diamagnetic
8.	Bis[1-(6-hydroxy-3-bromo- <i>m</i> -tolyl)ethylideneamine]Ni(II)	570	Diamagnetic
8d'	"	—	"
9.	Bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromo-phenyl)ethylideneoxime]Cu(II)	640	1.92
10.	Bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromo- <i>m</i> -tolyl)ethylideneoxime]Cu(II)	650	1.85
11.	Bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromo- <i>p</i> -tolyl)ethylideneoxime]Cu(II)	650	1.88
12.	Bis[1-(6-hydroxy- <i>m</i> -tolyl)ethylideneoxime]Cu(II)	645	1.86
13.	Bis[1-(2-hydroxy-3,5-dibromo phenyl)ethylideneoxime]Ni(II)	600	Diamagnetic
14.	Bis[1-(2-hydroxy-5-bromo- <i>m</i> -tolyl)ethylideneoxime]Ni(II)	610	Diamagnetic
15.	Bis[1-(2-hydroxy-3,5-dibromo- <i>p</i> -tolyl)ethylideneoxime]Ni(II)	610	Diamagnetic
16.	Bis[1-(6-hydroxy-3-bromo- <i>m</i> -tolyl)ethylideneoxime]Ni(II)	620	Diamagnetic

a', b', c', d'—Prepared from brominated ligand; 9, 10, 13, 14—prepared by direct bromination; 11, 12, 15, 16—prepared by amine exchange.

All compounds gave consistent elemental analysis.

shows that the bromination reaction takes place in Cu(II) complexes over benzene ring at position-5 only. However, only monobromo complexes were

formed with 3-methyl and 5-methyl substituted binary imine or oxime Ni(II) complexes; one of the positions 3 or 5 being already occupied by the methyl group. This shows that the bromination reaction takes place in Ni(II) complexes over benzene ring at positions 3 and 5. This is due to different orientation effect of phenolic oxygen (-O) and azomethine group (>C=N-).

Amine exchange takes place when brominated copper(II) and nickel(II) imine compounds are treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of sodium acetate. The H of the imine group is replaced by -OH oxime group.

The analysis, magnetic moments and spectral properties of the above bis-brominated imine or oxime complexes and the corresponding bis-complexes obtained by the reaction of metal ammine with brominated ligand are found to be similar.

All complexes are non-electrolyte in chloroform solution and addition of aqueous silver nitrate to an ethanolic solution of the brominated complex does not yield a precipitate. This shows that there is no free bromine in the complex or coordinated bromide ions thereby confirming that bromination of the benzene molecule has occurred.

The brominated nickel(II) imine and oxime complexes are typical product of the bromination reactions. Like [1-(2-hydroxy phenyl)ethylideneamine]-Ni(II)⁶, these compounds are diamagnetic and show a single absorption in the range 540-560 nm in imine complex and 600-620 nm in oxime complex in their visible spectra. This indicates the square planar geometry of these compounds.

All brominated copper(II) imine and oxime complexes are paramagnetic ($\mu=1.8$ to 1.95 B.M.) indicating the presence of one unpaired electron. There is no change in the paramagnetic value of brominated compounds of copper(II) complexes from those without bromo substitution. The visible absorption spectra of brominated compounds exhibit one broad band at 560 nm in case of imine compounds and at ~ 650 nm in case of oxime compounds¹¹.

The ir spectra of imine derivatives of 2-hydroxyacetophenone Schiff base compounds contain two characteristic strong bands at 1600 and 3300 cm^{-1} which are associated with the >C=N and N-H bond stretches⁹. Similarly, oxime complexes show one band at ~ 1625 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=N stretching¹². Substitution of bromine in the benzene ring at 3 and 5 positions or 3 or 5 position depending upon the substituents present, results in the increase of the C=N and N-H stretching frequencies. The ir spectra of the brominated complexes show these bands at 1610-1625 cm^{-1} in imine complex, 1640 cm^{-1} in oxime complex and 3310-3325 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=N and N-H, stretching, which are increased by 10 to 25 cm^{-1} unit.

The ir spectra of brominated bis-imine Schiff base complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) show a

N-H stretching band at ~ 3320 cm^{-1} . The disappearance of the 3320 cm^{-1} band after N-substitution reaction can be attributed to the replacement of the N-H hydrogen in brominated bis-copper(II) and nickel(II) imine Schiff base complexes by hydroxyl (-OH) groups.

Above results show that there is no effect of N-substituents on ring substitution reactions thereby suggesting that the orientation of the incoming bromine remains the same in imine (N-H) or oxime (N-OH) compounds.

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Nickel(II) Mixed Ligand Complexes with Schiff Bases Containing Nitrogen and Oxygen Donor Atoms†

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BIS Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxy acetophenone and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde are reported¹⁻⁸ to form coordination complexes with various bivalent metal ions. Similarly, mixed imine and aliphatic diamine Schiff base complexes derived from salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxy

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